

NOVITAS-ROYAL
RESEARCH ON YOUTH AND LANGUAGE

NOVITAS-ROYAL (RESEARCH ON YOUTH AND LANGUAGE)

ISSN: 1307-4733

OCTOBER 2023

VOLUME: 17

ISSUE: 2

CONTENTS

**Process-Genre Approach in Mixed-Ability Classes: Correlational Study
between EFL Academic Paragraph Reading and Writing**

Abduljalil Nasr HAZAEA | pp. 1-12

**Weathering the Storm: Unraveling the Challenges of EFL Student Teaching
in Ukraine**

Marianna LÓRINCZ & Oleh KOMAR | pp. 13-33

**Evaluating Oral English Program for Non-English Major Students: Focusing
on Self-Assessment of Students' Speaking Abilities and Their Needs**

La DUNIFA | pp. 34-49

**Variation in Academic Writing: A Corpus-Based Research on Syntactic
Features across Four Disciplinary Divisions**

Muhammad AHMAD, Muhammad Asim MAHMOOD & Ali Raza SIDDIQUE | pp. 50-65

**Unveiling the Metamorphosis: English Teachers' Shifting Identity in the
Context of Post-COVID-19 Distance Education**

Gamze ERDEM COŞGUN & Perihan SAVAŞ | pp. 66-79

**The Effects of Picture Dictionaries in Promoting Vocabulary Development
of EFL Learners at Tertiary Level**

Saban KARA & Turgay KUCUK | pp. 80-94

**Pre-service EFL Teachers' Immunity Perceptions Concerning Their
Perceived Teacher Commitment Levels Anxiety**

Aydan IRGATOĞLU & Özkan KIRMIZI | pp. 95-111

**Exploring EAP Students' Conceptualization of Sustainable Development
Goals: Implications for Higher Education**

Mehmet Galip ZORBA | pp. 112-127